

ADJUSTMENT AMONG PROSPECTIVE TEACHERS WITH RESPECT TO THEIR GENDER AND STREAM

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Abstract

This paper attempts to study the adjustment among prospective teachers with respect to their gender in Himachal Pradesh. The sample included 331 prospective teachers of Himachal Pradesh by employing random sampling techniques. Data were collected from B.Ed Colleges by using standardised questionnaire. The tool used for “teachers adjustment inventory scale” was developed by S.K Mangal. The findings of the study reveals that there is no significant difference in adjustment among prospective teachers with respect to their gender. It was found that there is no significant stream wise difference between the male and female prospective teachers in terms of their Adjustment. But on the other hand the mean scores of adjustment girls is higher than those from boys which indicate that the girls are better adjusted as compared to their boys counterpart.

Keywords: adjustment, gender, stream.

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Introduction

The word '**education**' has a very wide connotation. It is like a diamond that appears to be of a different colour when seen from a different angle. It is a key factor determining the nation's progress. Education plays an important role in the overall development of human beings. School education in the initial years helps in the formation of the personality of children whereas higher education shapes the children for facing the challenges of life. Adjustment, in psychology, refers to the behavioural process by which humans and other animals maintain equilibrium among their various needs or between their needs and the obstacles of their environments. Education is considered as a necessity in the present age of science and technology. In the past when this life was simple, education was considered as a luxury. It was available only too few fortunate persons. It was not education for masses. But, now it occupies an important place in life. It is education for masses. It is not neglected aspect of today. Quality of a nation depends upon the quality of education imparted to its citizen which in turns depends upon the quality of the teachers. The teacher is of paramount importance in any system of education. The whole system of education revolves around the teacher. The teacher is the pivot of any educational system.

Mahatma Gandhi said: Education is "the basic tool for development of consciousness and reconstruction of society". Teacher is a medium to achieve the goal. Hence, the quality of teacher education to provide teachers is an important component for the success of this programme.

The report of the **National Education Commission** (1964-66) states: "The destiny of India is now being shaped in her classrooms. This, we believe is no more rhetoric". The key player in the process is the teacher.

Teacher is a key figure in the life of a nation. For many reasons he has a unique place in the society. It has been seen in practical life that a child gives more weight aye to his teachers in comparison to his parents. If we want to have on idea about nation prosperity then we can have it only by looking at the conditions and to have it only by looking at the conditions and status of its teachers. Because a nation's well-being depends on the teacher's well-being. Teacher is a human being like others, have his own problem of adjustment.

A satisfactory adjustment is essential as in teaching, actually in the advancement in the field of education very much depends upon the degree of adjustment and satisfaction of those

who are in the field and are enhancing the cause of education. Adjusted teachers do much to bring about pupil adjustment and converse is also true. Whether or not a class is smooth running and effective would measure the degree of personal adjustment of the teachers.

The Review of Literature

Singh, H. (2003) conducted a study of stress among male and female teachers in relation to their personality needs and adjustment. He has assessed the stress among male and female teachers in relation to their personality needs and adjustment. Seven hundred twenty teachers (360 male and 360 female) of secondary schools / intermediate colleges and degree colleges of Meerut educational region were randomly selected and administered Meenakshi personality inventory and inventories to measure stress and adjustment, developed by researcher were used for data collection. Secondary school female teachers show significant negative relationship in their stress and adjustment. **Sabu & Jangaiah (2005)** conducted a study on adjustment and teachers stress. The objectives of the study were: (i) To find out the relation is any between the adjustment and stress of secondary school teachers. (ii) To find out the difference is any between the male and female teachers in respect of their adjustment and stress. The concerned study was undertaken on a sample of 60 secondary school teachers (25 graduate, 20 post graduates and 5 teacher training) to measure the adjustment and stress. The study revealed that the teachers with high adjustment experienced low adjustment. Major finding of the study indicated that there was a significant negative correlation between the adjustment and stress of secondary school teachers. The teacher with high adjustment had low stress and the teacher with high stress has low adjustment. There was no significant difference between male and female teachers in their adjustment. **Sindhu, I.S. (2005)** conducted a study of teachers motivation students adjustment and their academic achievement. Ram- Eash Journal of Education, 2(2), 19-23. The major findings were: Both male and female teachers were found to possess average or above average level of motivation to work. Most teachers displayed average and above average adjustments with school environment. The females displayed superior adjustment as compared to male. **Kuruvilla (2006)** found that sex and area of residence influenced the emotional adjustment of adolescent from his study on 980 10th std. students using standardized scale of emotional adjustment (kuruvilla 2002). Girls were found to have better adjustment than boys. **Singh (2006)** examined the effects of socio, emotional and socio emotional climate of the school and sex on the adjustment of students along with their interactions effects. Boys were significantly better

than girls in their health adjustment at different levels of socio-emotional climate of the school. **Raju and Rahamtulla (2007)** intended to examine the adjustment capacity of school students and found that adjustment of school children is primarily dependent on the school variables like the class in which they are studying, the medium of instruction, and the type of management of the school. **Niradhar Dey (2009)** conducted a study on assess the teacher adjustment and mental health of secondary school. He conducted a study on 120 teachers to assess the teacher adjustment and mental health of secondary school. Mangal teacher adjustment inventory and CE mental health scale of teachers were used. The findings reveal that mental health and teachers' adjustment is associated with each other. A mentally healthy teacher can be expected highly adjustable and vice-versa. The female teachers were more mentally healthy and highly adjustable. **Maureen et.al. (2011)** made a study on school adjustment in relation to academic achievement and gender which revealed that there were no significant differences between girls and boys in school adjustment. **Kaur (2012)** investigated the problems of adjustment in relation to achievement, sex and locality. He found that girls has more adjustment power than boys while locality does not influence adjustment power. **Peerzada (2013)** designed a study to compare the adjustment of science and social science higher secondary school teachers in different area like home adjustment, school adjustment, emotional adjustment etc. and showed that the social science teachers have more adjustment problems than science teachers.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To study gender-wise difference in adjustment among prospective teachers.
2. To study stream-wise difference in adjustment among prospective teachers.

HYPOTHESES OF THE STUDY

1. There will be no significant gender-wise difference in adjustment among prospective teachers.
2. There will be no significant stream- wise difference in adjustment among prospective teachers.

RESEARCH METHOD TO BE EMPLOYED: In the present investigation 'Survey Technique' under "Descriptive Method of Research" will be used.

SAMPLING: In the present investigation, the procedure of multistage sampling along with the process of stratified random sampling will be followed. At the first stage, five districts will be selected through stratified random sampling technique.

The researcher will select five district out of ten districts (except Kinnaur and Lahul-spiti) of Himachal Pradesh through random sampling procedure. The district Lahul-Spiti has no B.Ed. College. Hence, these two districts will not be taken in universe for sampling. From the sampled five districts, twenty five to thirty B.Ed. colleges will be selected by employing random sampling technique.

The prospective teachers studying in B.Ed. course will be selected by adopting stratified random sampling technique with proportional allocation. Firstly, the researcher will divide the population of prospective teachers in one institution into four strata on the basis of their gender and academic streams (Arts and Science) and then select 30% sample with proportional allocation from each of four stratum by employing random sampling technique. On an average, the researcher will try to include at least 700 prospective teachers from selected B.Ed colleges.

RESEARCH TOOLS TO BE USED: For measuring the Adjustment of Prospective Teachers, a standardized inventory by S.K Mangal will be used. This inventory consists of 70 items.

STATISTICAL TECHNIQUES TO BE EMPLOYED: In order to achieve the objectives of the present study, different types of statistical techniques will be employed. First of all, for checking the normality of the data certain descriptive statistics like mean, median, mode, SD, Q.D, Skewness and Kurtosis will be calculated on self-efficacy score and adjustment scores. Further for studying gender-wise, and stream-wise differences in adjustment of prospective teachers, the statistical technique of t-test will be applied. “Analysis of Variance” will be applied.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

SUMMARY OF THE RESULTS OF ANALYSIS OF VARIANCE FOR ADJUSTMENT OF PROSPECTIVE TEACHERS IN RELATION TO GENDER

Result of T- Test of Prospective teacher Adjustment scores By Gender

Sr. No	Variable	Mean	S.D	d.f	‘t’- Value
1	Male	38.63	31.276	329	.636
2	Female	40.64	13.178		

From the Table 1, it was found that there is no significant difference between the male and female prospective teachers in terms of their Adjustment , for table value 331, came out to be 0.636 which is much less than the table value (1.97) at 0.05 level of significance . Hence, it is evident that the null hypothesis (1) was accepted.

TABLE SHOWING THE MEAN SCORES OF ADJUSTMENT OF PROSPECTIVE TEACHERS IN RELATION TO GENDER

SUMMARY OF THE RESULTS OF ANALYSIS OF VARIANCE FOR ADJUSTMENT OF PROSPECTIVE TEACHERS IN RELATION TO STREAM

Result of T- Test of Prospective teacher Adjustment scores By Stream

Sr. No	Variable	Mean	S.D	d.f	't'- Value
1	Male	39.32	12.992	329	.649
2	Female	41.09	29.101		

From the Table 1, it was found that there is no significant difference between the male and female prospective teachers in terms of their Adjustment, for table value 331, came out to be 0.649 which is much less than the table value (1.97) at 0.05 level of significance. Hence, it is evident that the null hypothesis (2) was accepted.

TABLE SHOWING THE MEAN SCORES OF ADJUSTMENT OF PROSPECTIVE TEACHERS IN RELATION TO STREAM

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

From the result of the present study, it was concluded that adjustment is not being affected by gender and stream status of an individual. From the Table 1, it was found that there is no significant difference between the male and female prospective teachers in terms of their Adjustment [$t(331) = .636, p > 0.05$]. Both male and female prospective teachers are adjustable. Maureen et.al. (2011) supported this result and he found that made a study on school adjustment in relation to academic achievement and gender which revealed that there were no significant differences between girls and boys in school adjustment . However, Sindhu (2005) found that the female teachers displayed superior adjustment as compared to male teachers. It was found that there is no significant stream wise difference between the male and female prospective teachers in terms of their Adjustment [$t(331) = .649, p > 0.05$].

REFERENCES

- Jangaiah, C. (2005). Adjustment Teachers Stress. *Edutracks*, 4 (9), 32-35.
- Lal, K. (1985).** A study of adjustment problems of scheduled caste students in schools of Hariyana with reference to some personality variables. Ph.D. Edu. Del. U., 1985, As quoted in, *Fourth Survey of Research in Education (1983-88)*, 11, 1423.
- Pajares, F., and Miller, M. D. (1997). Gender differences in writing self-beliefs of elementary school students. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 91, 50-61.
- Reena (2011).** A study of the adjustment problems of college going students in relation to their cast and gender. *M.Ed. Dissertation*. Shimla: Himachal Pradesh University.

Subidhi, B. (1990). “A study of adjustment of college students in relation to their anxiety and intelligence.” *Indian Journal of Applied Psychology*, 27(2), 63-67.

Sarita, Kavita and Singh, Sn (2018). a study of an adjustment of prospective teachers in relation to introversion-extroversion. Retrieved from <https://www.semantic-scholar.org> on 16-03-2020.